

COLLECTIVISM, GENDER, REWARD AND PUNISHMENT ON FINANCIAL STATEMENT FRAUD

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Feb 21, 2024 Revised March 16, 2024 Accepted Apr 27, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Collectivism Gender Reward Punishment Financial Statement Fraud</p>	<p>Collectivism, Gender, Reward and Punishment on Financial Statement Fraud. Financial statement fraud is a deliberate omission in presenting data either in the form of disclosures or amounts in financial statements that are designed to cause losses to users of financial statements. This study aims to determine: The Effect of Collectivism on Financial Statement Fraud, The Effect of Gender on Financial Statement Fraud, The Effect of Reward on Financial Statement Fraud, The Effect of Punishment on Financial Statement Fraud. The data analysis technique in this study used multiple linear regression with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). The results showed that there was no effect of Collectivism on Financial Statement Fraud, there was no effect of Gender on Financial Statement Fraud, there was an effect of Reward on Financial Statement Fraud, there was an effect of Punishment on Financial Statement Fraud. These results are expected to provide recommendations for students in evaluating themselves regarding the importance of ethics and the character of accounting students in reducing the intention to commit fraudulent behavior.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <div style="text-align: right;"> </div>

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INTRODUCTION

In a profit-making or non-profit organization or company, there must be a desire to achieve a goal. Generally, this goal has been designed since the beginning of the organization. This is because the company or organization makes goals as one of the main elements. If all individual components within the organization can manage their resources, then what is the goal of the organization can be easily achieved. A fraud or unethical act can be minimized at work if the individuals in the organization can be directed in accordance with the policies made by the organization.

For people in today's society, an action that is enough to attract the interest of the general public in various circles is fraud cases. A form of lying behavior that is carried out intentionally and can have a detrimental impact on the victim but has a beneficial impact on the perpetrator can be called fraud.

According to the Association of Certified Fraud Examination (ACFE) in 2019, which conducted a study of the Indonesian Fraud Survey (SFI). However, the results of the survey can show that there is quite a lot of fraud in Indonesia and the case that causes the biggest loss is in the case of corruption which reaches 64%. Then the next type of fraud is embezzlement of assets in the government or in companies with a percentage of 28.9%, while in the case of fraudulent financial reporting it reaches 6.7%. But judging from the results of the review, there are differences in the 2018 Report to The Nations, which found that the most cases of fraud occurred in cases of asset embezzlement which reached a percentage of 89%, then followed by cases of corruption of 38% and then in cases of fraudulent financial reporting or financial statement reporting of 10%. However, there are still many cases in government or companies such as cases of fraudulent financial reporting in Indonesia. So that in January 2020, Indonesia received a score of 40 and was ranked 85 out of 180 countries, which can be seen in the Corruption Perception Index (CPI). Surveys and research conducted by ACFE Global show that 5% of the revenue of organizations / companies are victims of fraud cases every year. However, state-owned or private companies are also still not free from the risk of fraudulent behavior, which according to the website of the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP). (ACFE Indonesia Chapter, 2020).

To determine the existence of fraud in the resulting financial statements, the analysis method that can be used is by applying the fraud triangle theory. This theory is an idea or idea that studies the causes of fraud. The Indonesian Institute of Certified Public Accountants (IAPI) is an association of Indonesian public accountants who issued Audit Standard (SA) 240 with an explanation of the presentation of fraud factors using the fraud triangle theory. Donald R Cressey who put forward this idea for the first time in 1953. The concept of the fraud triangle theory is then outlined in Statement of Auditing Standards (SAS) No. 99 which explains the description of fraud factors based on this theory which is divided into three parts, namely opportunity, pressure, and rationalization. (IAPI, 2014).

In fact, individuals who carry out fraud behavior are not individual, but they work together (Collectivism) to benefit from these actions, where the action is obtained from the influence of subjective norm. Collectivism is a culture that is quite prominent in Indonesia. One of the facts obtained is that collectivist students tend to be positively related to fraudulent or unethical behavior. (Ama, 2022).

So collectivism can be interpreted as a form of concern from an individual for the group with the reward of loyalty. So that these individuals place the interests of the group above personal interests and try to protect each other. (Rizki & Mas'ud, 2016). In the case of fraud that is rampant, especially in Indonesia, it is very difficult to prevent this action if it is done in a group rather than individuals who commit fraud alone. Because in terms of collectivism, it has a positive influence on fraud behavior. (Rizki & Mas'ud, 2016)..

However, this study states that collectivism has a significant effect on fraud behavior. Meanwhile, research conducted by (Nurdianti & Ilyas, 2019) collectivism has no effect on fraudulent behavior.

Someone who commits fraud behavior can be caused by two factors, namely internal and external factors. Some of the internal factors that have an influence on fraud are Gender. The difference in gender is a factor that can affect fraud behavior. Gender is a personality trait, expectations and behavior related to a person's gender in the environment where they are in society. (Dewi Kusuma Wardani, 2022). Gender differences are based on biological factors, the learning process and a combination of these two factors. So that the expectations of men and women towards gender interpretation are that men are rational, masculine, dignified and strong. Women, on the other hand, are motherly, gentle, graceful and emotional. But some of the above characteristics can change based on experience and the surrounding environment.

Gender offers a different perspective by providing insight into a situation. That gender roles of masculinity and feminism can influence a man or woman in making a decision. Men tend to break the rules as long as they have achieved their goals, while women will be more likely to have a cautious attitude. At this time men and women have the same position, so quite a lot of women can occupy important positions in a company or organization. Then it can raise a question whether they can tolerate unethical behavior in carrying out their duties. (Andayani & Fitria Sari, 2019). However, research conducted by (Indiraswari, 2021) has a negative influence on fraud. Meanwhile, research conducted by (Dewi Kusuma Wardani, 2022) stated that gender has no influence on cheating behavior because gender is purely of an individual's own nature.

Some of the most common problems in companies are how to manage personnel management, so that employees can perform their duties as well as possible to achieve certain goals set by the company. There is a fairly close correlation between rewards and employee achievement, so companies must have an effective strategy for managing human resources. This strategy aims to encourage each individual to do work in accordance with the procedures and those set by the company to avoid fraud.

One of the efforts to improve the performance of each individual in an organization is through the implementation of rewards and punishments. These two words have opposite meanings but are interrelated. So that both have similarities in their role in motivating employees to improve the quality of performance and can have an obligation to the work that has been entrusted by the company. Reward and punishment are not allowed to be given only on a like or dislike basis by the company. Because if the provision of rewards and punishments is carried out unfairly, it can lead to social jealousy between employees so that it has a negative impact on work relationships and results in a decrease in employee performance. (Ihsan, 2019). However, research conducted by (Egita, E & Magfiroh, 2018) stated that reward and punishment have a negative influence on fraud. Meanwhile, research conducted by C reward and punishment has a positive and significant effect on fraudulent financial reporting.

Positive and negative incentives can affect employees in an agency, positive incentives can be called "rewards" are the result of an increase in satisfaction obtained from individual needs. However, the opposite is a negative incentive which can also be called a "punishment" which is the result of reducing the satisfaction obtained from needs. Incentives in the form of rewards are an incentive to meet a person's needs that may not be available if that person is not a member of the organization. Some of the problems that can be identified in this study include financial statement fraud can increase in an agency if employees do not get incentives in the form of rewards (bonuses, allowances, promotions) and punishment incentives (deductions, warning letters, suspensions) appropriately. In addition, the amount of compensation agreed upon by the agency and employees has not been found, thus making employees more likely to demand greater salaries and compensation because they are judged by their performance. However, the agency will maintain salary and compensation if each individual does not have a boost in work motivation, which is expected in the future employees can work in accordance with the provisions made by the company. (Noto, 2016).

In a company, the role of an accountant is very important because it can increase transparency in the financial statements needed by users of financial statements, besides that an honest attitude in the work done is also needed by accountants. Therefore, accounting students play an important role in the current study because to become a prospective accountant, they must know how to make decisions so that they can overcome the problem of fraud in financial reporting. (Saputra, Dicky. Nurlina, Lenny Hasan, SE, 2017).

This research refers to research conducted by (Damara, 2020). So that previous research with the research currently being conducted has similarities such as the use of independent variables, namely reward and punishment and the dependent variable, namely financial statement fraud or financial statement fraud. The difference in this study lies in the addition of independent variables, namely the Collectivism and Gender variables and expanding the research object because the previous research was only conducted at one university so that for the current study the researchers used objects at three different universities. The addition of these variables is supported by research from (Avitasari, 2022) that a culture of collectivism has implications for fraud behavior in employees in a company. Which means, both men and women have a tendency towards fraudulent behavior. So that the higher the collectivism, the greater the tendency towards fraudulent behavior.

So this study has the aim of knowing the effect of Collectivism on financial statement fraud, knowing the effect of Gender on financial statement fraud, knowing the effect of Reward on financial statement fraud, and also knowing the effect of Punishment on financial statement fraud. So that this research is expected to be useful and contribute to the development of science in the field of behavioral accounting, besides that it is intended to be a reference for future research focused on the field of behavioral accounting.

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Effect of Collectivism on Financial Statement Fraud

In Collectivism, an organization is more important than the individual, who must fulfill his or her personal needs and desires in accordance with the goals of the organization. From a collectivist point of view, the well-being or dignity of the organization is considered to transcend the individual. (Nurdianti & Ilyas, 2019). In the act of fraud behavior, someone more often does it in groups and protects each other. So that in research conducted by (Tonasa, Kanivia, Setyorini, & ..., 2022) shows that a culture of collectivism affects the tendency of fraudulent behavior.

H1 : Collectivism affects Financial Statement Fraud.

The Effect of Gender on Financial Statement Fraud

Gender can be called a perception used to identify, explain and describe the differences between men and women. With the existence of different concepts between an individual and another individual, it has an impact on various things that are closely related to a person's psychology. So that gender differences can be seen from the person's psychology (Dewi Kusuma Wardani, 2022). For example, there are differences between men and women in terms of the tendency to commit accounting fraud. Men are more likely to have the intention to commit fraud (Andayani & Fitria Sari, 2022). (Andayani & Fitria Sari, 2019).. This is in accordance with research conducted by (Merawati & Mahaputra, 2017) which states that gender has an effect on fraud.

H2 : Gender has an effect on Financial Statement Fraud.

The Effect of Reward on Financial Statement Fraud

Giving rewards is positive feedback given by the company for the achievements made by employees. The rewards given by the company can be in the form of material or non-material. (Reshie, S., 2020). According to Reinforcement theory, people are motivated to perform certain behaviors because they are associated with the rewards that have existed for this behavior. (Wahyuningsih, 2017). So that giving rewards can motivate someone to give their best performance so that job satisfaction and social status or employee achievement increase and will minimize fraud. (Damara, 2020). In accordance with research conducted by (Noto, 2016) that reward affects financial reporting fraud.

H3 : Reward affects Financial Statement Fraud

The Effect of Punishment on Financial Statement Fraud

Punishment is a negative reinforcer that is needed in the company. The punishment referred to here is not like a prison sentence or cutting off hands, but rather one that is educational in nature. (Situmeang, 2022). Punishment can be used to motivate employees to avoid attitudes that can violate regulations, one of which is fraudulent behavior. In accordance with research conducted by [21] states that punishment has an influence on fraud.

H4 : Punishment affects Financial Statement Fraud.

Figure 1. Research conceptual framework

METHODS

The population in this study were students majoring in accounting at Muhammadiyah Universities in East Java. However, researchers took the population in students at three different universities, namely Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo, Muhammadiyah University of Malang, and Muhammadiyah University of Jember. This study uses population data totaling 550 students. So that the sample obtained in this study amounted to 232 through calculations using the slovin formula. This research data comes from questionnaires distributed via g-from with the criteria that active students in semester 7 and have taken behavioral accounting courses. The research was conducted from January 2023 to February 2023.

Respondents are asked to fill in the answers to the questions listed in the questionnaire and the researcher will take back the questionnaire within a predetermined time frame, namely one month from the distribution of the questionnaire. There are two parts in the questionnaire, namely a questionnaire describing the respondent's self-description and then containing several questions relevant to the relationship between collectivism, gender, reward and punishment with financial statement fraud. This

questionnaire uses a Likert scale and has five value scales, namely value (1) with a strongly disagree indicator to value (4) with a strongly agree indicator.

Figure 1 shows the independent and dependent variables that will be tested in this study. Based on this figure, there are four independent variables in this study, namely the first, Collectivism. In the company, collectivism is a belief that members have in an organization, they think that the association is the most important thing in the organization. Moreover, they also have a business for the common good, not only for personal gain. (Sutampi, Priyatama, & Astriana, 2019). The second is Gender is an individual characteristic that is obtained from within a person and is accompanied by self-understanding, so that based on gender a self-understanding that is owned can influence in an assessment. (Ayem & Rumdoni, 2021). The third is Reward, which can be referred to as an award obtained from the company to the achievement of employee achievements which is considered as a reward for the performance that has been done optimally. (Kawulur, Areros, & Pio, 2018).. The fourth, Punishment, is an act of unwanted consequences and causes discomfort as a result of certain behaviors given by someone in authority within the company. If the organization/company uses punishment effectively, the behavior of individuals in the organization can be controlled. However, punishment must be carried out carefully and objectively obtained from all aspects along with the situations and conditions that occur. (Situmeang, 2022). Meanwhile, the dependent variable in this study is financial statement fraud. According to SAS No. 99, deliberate negligence in presenting data either in the form of disclosures or amounts in financial statements that are designed to cause losses to users of financial statements can be called financial statement fraud (AICPA, 2002). (AICPA, 2002)..

NO	Variables	Indicator	Source
1.	Collectivism (X1)	1. Horizontal collectivism: Looking out for each other's welfare, enjoying spending time together, prioritizing others' happiness over one's own. 2. Vertical collectivism: having a sense of community in every situation, and respecting group decisions.	(Tonasa et al., 2022)
2.	Gender (X2)	<i>Gender</i> variables do not use indicators because <i>gender</i> variables are included in ordinal data.	(Tutik Fardiana, 2019)

3.	Reward (X3)	Incentives, benefits, interpersonal rewards, and promotions	(Pratama & Sukarno, 2021)
4.	Punishment (X4)	Light punishment, medium punishment, heavy punishment.	(Pratama & Sukarno, 2021)
5.	Financial Statement Fraud (Y)	Data manipulation and work system violations	(Damara, 2020)

After describing the variables, the next step is to identify the test equation. The equation can be formed based on variable identification as follows:

$$FSF = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Description:

FSF= Financial Statement Fraud

α = Constant

X1 = Collectivism

X2 = Gender

X3 = Reward

X4 = Punishment

ε = Error

β = Regression Coefficient

For the next stage, the data will be tabulated and processed using the multiple linear regression analysis method with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) as a tool for analyzing data. This method was chosen because this study uses more than one independent variable and can make it easier for researchers to determine the direction and level of influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Before the influence test is carried out, identification will be carried out for the validity test and reliability test of all questions that have been listed on the distributed questionnaires.

If the question has met the criteria of the two tests, the next step is to test the hypothesis, namely the T (Partial) test and the Determination test, the T test is used to determine the significant role partially between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Hypothesis testing is done by comparing t.count with t.table. If t.count is greater than t.table, it means that there is a strong reason for the hypothesis (H) to be accepted. In addition, it can also use a significant test. Provided that if the significant value is less than 0.05 alpha, it means that there is a reason for the hypothesis (H) to be accepted, otherwise if it is more than 0.05 alpha, the hypothesis (H) is rejected. While the determination test to determine the ability of the model to explain the variation in the dependent variable whether the closer to the value of one, the independent variable is considered to have a good ability to explain the dependent variable and vice versa. (Iman White Devil, 2013).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

This research was conducted at Muhammadiyah Universities in East Java, namely at Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo, Muhammadiyah University of Jember and Muhammadiyah University of Malang. Where this research is aimed at Accounting Study Program Students at the University. Sampling in this study using the slovin formula because there is a large enough population so that a formula is needed to get a small sample but can represent the entire population. So that there are characteristics of the respondents in 232 questionnaires that can be used for processing, namely:

Table 2. Respondent Characteristics

Criteria	Frequency (people)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	54	23,3
Female	178	76,7
Higher Education		
Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo	118	50,9
Muhammadiyah University of Jember	38	16,4
University of Muhammadiyah Malang	76	32,8

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

It can be seen from table 2 that the respondents who participated in this study were more dominant women and obtained 178 or 76.7% but men were only 54 or 23.3%. then based on Higher Education, Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo as many as 118 or 50.9% were the next most respondents at Muhammadiyah University of Jember as many as 38 or 16.4% and at Muhammadiyah University of Malang as many as 76 or 32.8%.

Table 2. Descriptive Data Analysis Results

	N	Total.X1	Total.X3	Total.X4	Total.Y
Mean	232	16,19	18,79	16,51	18,72
Std. Deviation	232	2,230	1,936	2,160	2,234
Minimum	232	11	8	7	7
Maximum	232	25	20	20	20
Valid N (listwise)	232				

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

Data Quality Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is carried out to assess whether a questionnaire is valid or not. So that if the instrument is declared valid, the instrument will measure the variable to be tested appropriately.

a. Collectivism (X1)

Table 4. Collectivism Validity Test Results (X1)

Question item	r Count	r Table	Description
1	0,675	0,138	Valid
2	0,615	0,138	Valid
3	0,202	0,138	Valid
4	0,643	0,138	Valid
5	0,553	0,138	Valid
6	0,229	0,138	Valid
7	0,990	0,138	Valid

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

All question items on the collectivism variable are declared valid because r Count on each question is greater than r Table.

b. Gender (X2)

The gender variable uses a dummy variable. So that this variable does not have indicators or question items, only the code given is 1 for men and 2 for women.

c. Reward (X3)

Table 4. Reward Validity Test Results (X3)

Question item	r Count	r Table	Description
1	0,782	0,138	Valid
2	0,821	0,138	Valid
3	0,821	0,138	Valid
4	0,805	0,138	Valid
5	0,737	0,138	Valid

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

In this table, it can be seen that the value of *r* Count on all reward variable question items is greater than *r* Table. So it can be interpreted that all indicators or question items that test the *reward* variable are declared valid.

d. Punishment (X4)

Table 5. *Punishment* Validity Test Results (X4)

Question item	<i>r</i> Count	<i>r</i> Table	Description
1	0,614	0,138	Valid
2	0,676	0,138	Valid
3	0,148	0,138	Valid
4	0,711	0,138	Valid
5	0,794	0,138	Valid

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

It can be seen in the table above that the value of *r* Count on each question item is greater than *r* Table. This means that all indicators or question items that measure the *punishment* variable are declared valid.

e. *Financial Statement Fraud* (Y)

Table 6. *Financial Statement Fraud* Validity Test Results (Y)

Question item	<i>r</i> Count	<i>r</i> Table	Description
1	0,838	0,138	Valid
2	0,807	0,138	Valid
3	0,828	0,138	Valid
4	0,877	0,138	Valid
5	0,862	0,138	Valid

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

The table above shows the value of *r* Count on each question item is greater than *r* Table. So it can be interpreted that all indicators or question items that measure *financial statement fraud* variables are declared valid.

4.2.2.2 Reliability Test Results

The reliability test is carried out to find out further whether the results obtained in the study can be believed to be true so that they can get quite different results if used repeatedly on the same subject. The results of the reliability test on the questionnaire for each variable can be seen below:

Table 7. Data Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Description
Collectivism (X1)	0,842	Reliable
Reward (X2)	0,775	Reliable
Punishment (X3)	0,779	Reliable
Financial Statement Fraud (Y)	0,779	Reliable

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

It can be seen in the table above that the reliability test results show the *Cronbach's Alpha* value for all variables above 0.700. If *Cronbach's Alpha* is 0.70 - 0.90,

it can be stated that the variable has high reliability.

Hypothesis Testing

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression analysis is used in order to see whether or not there is an influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable with the help of SPSS (version 23). The results of multiple linear regression analysis are listed in table 8.

Table 8. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error
	B	
(Constant)	2,411	1,258
Total.X1	-0,080	0,041
Total.X2	0,185	0,212
Total.X3	0,766	0,060
Total.X4	0,174	0,053

a. Dependent Variable: Total.Y

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

It can be seen from the multiple linear regression test table that the following multiple regression equation is obtained:

$$Y = 2.411 - 0.080 X1 + 0.185X2 + 0.766 X3 + 0.174 X4 + \epsilon$$

Test t (Partial)

Table 9. T Test Results (Partial)

Model	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta		
(Constant)		1,917	0,057
Total.X1	-0,080	-1,966	0,050
Total.X2	0,035	0,873	0,384
Total.X3	0,664	12,727	0,000
Total.X4	0,169	3,271	0,001

a. Dependent Variable: Total.Y

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

It can be seen from the table above that The tcount of the Collectivism variable (X1) is -1.966 while the ttable is 0.1971 so that the tcount < ttable with a significant for the collectivism variable of 0.050 is equal to the significant level of 0.05. So that H1 is rejected, it can be concluded from the partial test results that collectivism (X1) has no effect on *financial statement fraud*.

Based on the table above, it can be obtained that the Thitung of the Gender (X2) variable is 0.873, while the Ttable is 0.1971 so that Thitung < Ttable with a significant for the gender variable of 0.384 greater than the significant level of 0.05. So H2 is rejected, so it can be concluded that partially gender (X2) has no effect on *financial statement fraud*.

The Reward variable (X3) has a Thitung value of 12.727 while the Ttable is

0.1971 so that $T_{hitung} > T_{table}$ with a significant *reward* variable of 0.000 is smaller than the 0.05 significant level. So H3 is accepted, so it can be concluded that partially *reward* (X3) has a positive and significant effect on *financial statement fraud*.

In the *Punishment* variable (X4) has a T_{hitung} value of 3.271 while the T_{table} is 0.1971 so that $T_{hitung} > T_{table}$ with a significant for the *punishment* variable of 0.001 is smaller than the significant level of 0.05. So H4 is accepted, so it can be concluded that partially *punishment* (X4) has a positive and significant effect on *financial statement fraud*.

R Square (Coefficient of Determination)

Table 10. Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.796 ^a	0,634	0,628	1,363	0,634	98,355	4	227	0,000	2,039

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total_X1, Total_X2, Total_X3, Total_X4

b. Dependent Variable: Total.Y

Source: SPSS processed data (version 23), 2023

From table 10 it is known that the coefficient of determination (*Adjusted R Square*) is 0.628 or 62.8%. This means that 62.8% of the *financial statement fraud* variable can be explained or influenced by the *collectivism, gender, reward and punishment variables*, while the remaining 37.2% is explained or influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Collectivism on *Financial Statement Fraud*

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out. It can be seen that there is no effect of *collectivism* on *financial statement fraud*. So that it is in line with research conducted by (Avtasari, 2022) which proves that *collectivism* has no effect on *financial statement fraud*. So the results of this study confirm that *personality factors* have a greater influence than *environmental factors* such as the tendency to group together. (Nurdianti & Ilyas, 2019).

The Effect of Gender on *Financial Statement Fraud*

Based on these results, it can be seen that *gender* has no influence on *financial*

statement fraud. These results are in line with research conducted by (Dewi Kusuma Wardani, 2022) which proves that gender has no effect on *financial statement fraud*. And also in accordance with research (Mahsifah & Mahmudi, 2021) which explains that *gender* is purely obtained from the nature of the individual itself. So that *gender* is influenced by the education, experience, and culture of the individual.

The Effect of Reward on *Financial Statement Fraud*

From the results of this study, it can be seen that *reward* has a positive influence on *financial statement fraud*. So that these results are in line with research conducted by (Damara, 2020) which proves that *reward* has a positive effect on *financial statement fraud*. This finding is in accordance with the *Fraud Triangle Theory* which consists of 3 components, one of which is *pressure* (pressure) which suggests that someone has the urge to cheat due to personal financial problems. So with the provision of *rewards* that are applied such as giving bonuses and increasing positions, according to the perceptions of Accounting Students at Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo, Muhammadiyah University of Jember and Muhammadiyah University of Malang, it can further combat *financial statement fraud*, both avoiding acts of misuse or manipulation of data in making financial statements, besides that Accounting Students will be more motivated to work in accordance with the rules. (Ningsih, Ammar, & Irwan, 2017)..

The Effect of Punishment on *Financial Statement Fraud*

It can be seen based on the results of this study that *punishment* has a positive influence on *financial statement fraud*. These results are in line with research conducted by (Prabowo & Priantinah, 2018) which proves that *punishment* has a positive effect on *financial statement fraud*. With these findings in accordance with the *Fraud Triangle Theory* which consists of 3 components, one of which is *Opportunity*, which suggests that someone will look for opportunities to commit fraud if there is poor internal control and system weaknesses. So from these results it can show that the existence of *punishments* applied to each individual such as reprimands, warning letters, suspensions, and dismissals can further minimize a person's intention to look for opportunities to commit fraud and can combat *financial statement fraud* both to avoid acts of misuse or manipulation of data in making *financial* statements. (Ningsih et al., 2017).

Descriptive Statistics Results

Descriptive analysis has the aim of making it easier for researchers to obtain an overview based on the tendency or tendency of the results of respondents' answers about all variable items in the research to be used. Below is a description of the descriptive analysis results of each research variable.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Accounting Students' perceptions of Collectivism, Gender, Reward and Punishment on Financial Statement Fraud. The subjects of this study were accounting students at Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo, Muhammadiyah University of Jember and Muhammadiyah University of Malang. By using a sample of 232 respondents to answer the research questions that have been formulated. Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, several conclusions can be drawn. The conclusions of this study are as follows:

1. Collectivism has no effect on Financial Statement Fraud. This means that the higher or lower collectivism has no influence on the occurrence of Financial Statement Fraud.
2. Gender has no effect on Financial Statement Fraud. This means that neither men nor women have an influence on the occurrence of Financial Statement Fraud.
3. Reward has a significant effect on Financial Statement Fraud. This means that the higher the reward, the smaller the occurrence of Financial Statement Fraud.
4. Punishment has a significant effect on Financial Statement Fraud. This means that the higher the punishment, the smaller the occurrence of Financial Statement Fraud.

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